

ISic3657

I.Sicily inscription 3657

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

stone

Object

sima

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

on the sima of the Temple of Demeter

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale
Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR139045

1. δ

2. ε

3. υ

4. γ

5. ε, η

6.

7. τ

8. ι

9. ζ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 139045

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 134-135 fig.27

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